

CLINICAL AND ANAMNESTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PNEUMONIA WITH BRONCHO-OBSTRUCTIVE SYNDROME IN YOUNG CHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15164013>

Abstract. *The highest seasonal incidence of acute respiratory viral infections (ARVI) occurs between October and April. Complications following ARVI, particularly bronchopulmonary pathologies, represent a pressing issue in pediatrics. Respiratory system diseases remain among the most common pathologies in the pediatric population, ranking first in morbidity among children under the age of 14, with a rising trend, especially in young children, making it a recognized cause of morbidity and mortality [1, 3, 4]. Frequent ARVI episodes affect the reactivity of the child's body, leading to recurrent pneumonia in 10-30% of cases. This contributes to the formation of chronic infection foci, delays in physical and psychomotor development, and social maladaptation [2, 5]. Pneumonia is one of the most frequently encountered bronchopulmonary pathologies. The incidence of pneumonia is approximately 15–20 cases per 1,000 children in the first three years of life and about 5–6 cases per 1,000 children over the age of three [5-7].*

Keywords: *pneumonia, vomiting, regurgitation, congenital heart defects, rickets, vitamin deficiencies.*

Introduction. Predisposing factors for pneumonia in children include perinatal pathology, aspiration syndrome caused by vomiting and regurgitation, congenital heart defects, rickets, vitamin deficiencies, and various deficiency conditions, including secondary immunodeficiency states. The severity of pneumonia is determined by pulmonary and cardiac insufficiency, intoxication, and complications such as pleurisy, pulmonary destruction, and infectious-toxic shock. Mortality from acute pneumonia in children under one year of age remains significantly high. According to WHO reports from 2010, its share in mortality structure is 3-4% in developed countries and 10-20% in developing countries annually [2, 6, 8].

Broncho-obstructive syndrome (BOS) is a common pathology in children, particularly in early childhood, and plays a leading role in the development of respiratory disorders [1, 3, 5]. The high incidence of BOS, its severe clinical course, and the risk of disease development highlight the relevance of this issue. The primary cause of BOS in children is acute obstructive bronchitis (AOB), which complicates 30-50% of respiratory infections (RI) in young children [2, 9, 11, 21]. Broncho-obstruction leads to a wide range of bronchopulmonary diseases, including congenital and hereditary pathologies, delayed bronchial development, respiratory distress syndrome, immunodeficiency conditions, aspiration of foreign bodies, perinatal pathology, gastroesophageal reflux, enlargement of intrathoracic lymph nodes, thymic hyperplasia, and tumors [2, 3, 24]. The similarity of causes of bronchial obstruction in different diseases creates difficulties in early diagnosis and the selection of appropriate treatment strategies, which may result in prolonged or recurrent courses of certain diseases.

Objective of the Study. To examine the clinical and anamnestic characteristics of pneumonia in young children with broncho-obstructive syndrome.

Materials and Methods. The study included 88 children aged 1 to 3 years who were treated at Zangiota No. 2 Infectious Disease Hospital in the Pediatric Department of Somatic Pathologies, Tashkent. The patients were divided into two groups:

- **Group 1:** 56 children (63.6%) diagnosed with community-acquired acute pneumonia with broncho-obstructive syndrome (BOS) (main group).
- **Group 2:** 32 children (36.4%) diagnosed with acute pneumonia without BOS (control group).

Clinical and anamnestic data were collected, including patient complaints, disease history, and objective examination findings. Instrumental examinations included chest radiography, and laboratory test results were analyzed. Statistical processing of the results was performed using Microsoft Excel 7.0 statistical software, with the significance of differences assessed using parametric and non-parametric tests.

Results and Discussion. An analysis of medical histories and parental interviews revealed that 89% of the studied children had a history of frequent acute respiratory infections (ARI) and were hospitalized in severe condition due to pronounced endogenous intoxication, respiratory failure (RF), hemodynamic disturbances, and microcirculatory disorders. The majority of children in the study groups exhibited a gradual onset of pneumonia, as indicated by the timing of hospitalization.

- In **Group 1**, 78.3% of children were hospitalized within the first 3-5 days of illness, while 21.7% had a history of obstructive bronchitis.
- In **Group 2**, 53.4% of children were hospitalized on the 7th day of illness, while 46.6% were admitted on the 10th day.

Analysis of obstetric and somatic history showed that mothers of children in the main group had a higher number of risk factors compared to the control group. Specifically:

- Pregnancy termination was more frequent in the main group (40.0% vs. 15.0%, $p < 0.05$).
- Gestosis was more common in the main group (46.6% vs. 20.0%, $p < 0.001$).
- Fetoplacental insufficiency was significantly higher in the main group (45.0% vs. 18.3%, $p < 0.001$).
- Mild and moderate anemia were more frequently diagnosed in mothers of the main group (53.3% and 25.0%, respectively, vs. 15.7% and 6.5% in the control group, $p < 0.05$).
- The proportion of mothers with extragenital pathology was higher in the main group (41.6% vs. 16.6%, $p < 0.001$).

Regardless of the group, potential maternal diseases included:

- Arterial hypertension (14.5% and 10.2%).
- Urinary system pathology (65.4% and 36.2%, $p < 0.001$).
- Endocrine system diseases (10.7% and 12.2% in cases of hypo- and hyperthyroidism).
- Nutritional obesity/excess body weight (18.3% and 13.3%).

Analysis of the neonatal period revealed that the proportion of firstborns was higher among mothers in the main group (68.3%) compared to the control group (40.0%, $p < 0.001$).

The frequency of cesarean section delivery did not show any significant differences between the groups (30.0% and 32.1%, respectively, $p > 0.05$). Birth asphyxia (Apgar score <7 at the first minute) was observed in 15.0% of cases in the main group compared to 3.33% in the control group ($p < 0.01$). Prematurity (gestational age 32–34 weeks and birth weight <2000 g) was more frequently registered in the main group (40.0%) compared to the control group (15.0%). Perinatal central nervous system (CNS) lesions were also more frequently diagnosed in the main group (43.3%) than in the control group (28.3%).

One of the risk factors for frequent bronchopulmonary pathologies in early childhood is artificial feeding, improper introduction of complementary foods, and consumption of solid food at an inappropriate age, which increases susceptibility to respiratory infections (frequent acute respiratory infections [ARIs], bronchitis). The type of feeding in children under one year plays a decisive role in child health. Analysis of the feeding patterns in the studied groups showed that the proportion of children who were on artificial feeding from birth was significantly higher in the main group (48.3%) compared to the control group (21.6%).

By the age of one, manifestations of rickets of 1st-2nd degree were diagnosed in 51.6% of frequently ill children (main group), while in the control group, this indicator was 25.0%. Comorbid pathologies in early childhood are one of the main causes of lower respiratory tract infections. Among the common manifestations of diathesis (constitutional anomalies), lymphatic-hypoplastic diathesis, combined with exudative-catarrhal diathesis, was observed in 55.0% of cases in the main group compared to 18.3% in the control group. The frequency of isolated exudative-catarrhal diathesis was 25.0% in the main group and 23.3% in the control group, while isolated lymphatic-hypoplastic diathesis was found in 20.5% of children in the main group and 13.3% in the control group.

Children in the main group had higher rates of ENT pathologies: acute pharyngitis (31.6%), adenoiditis (1st-2nd degree) (38.3%), and acute otitis media (15.1%), compared to the control group, where these conditions were observed in 10.0%, 23.5%, and 10.5% of children, respectively. Notably, the groups differed in the frequency of recurrent pneumonia. In the main group, 68.3% of frequently ill children had recurrent pneumonia (≥ 2 times per year), compared to only 12% in the control group. Additionally, 31.6% of children in the main group had occasional ARIs.

According to parental surveys, in 67% of cases, children in both groups had preceding catarrhal symptoms of the upper respiratory tract before hospitalization, which were significantly more common in the main group (83.3%) than in the control group (16.4%). The main symptoms of pneumonia in the examined patients were febrile fever, which was more frequently diagnosed in the main group (65.0%) compared to the control group (38.3%); intoxication symptoms (80.0% in the main group vs. 55.0% in the control group), reduced appetite (41.6% vs. 25.0%), and emotional lability (41.6% vs. 25.0%). Unproductive cough was observed in 86.6% of children in the main group and 76.6% in the control group ($p > 0.01$).

Dyspnea was also more common in the main group (88.3%) compared to the control group (70.0%). Overall, all clinical symptoms, except for unproductive cough, were more frequently recorded in the main group (78.9%) than in the control group (45.8%). Children in the main group also exhibited increased sweating (58.3%) compared to the control group (38.3%).

Acrocyanosis, perioral cyanosis, and skin mottling were more frequently observed in the main group, occurring in 36.6%, 41.6%, and 51.6% of cases, respectively, compared to 13.3%,

21.6%, and 25.0% in the control group ($p < 0.05$, $p < 0.001$, $p < 0.01$). Lymph node enlargement was detected in most children in the main group (56.0%) compared to 23.3% in the control group. Chest deformity associated with subacute rickets was observed in 38.3% of children in the main group, compared to 12.0% in the control group.

It should be noted that protein-energy malnutrition (PEM) of -2SD was observed in 20.0% of children in the main group and only in 10.3% of children in the comparison group. Excess body weight (PEM + 2SD) was recorded in 45.5% of children in the main group and only in 7.8% of children in the comparison group, indicating a higher prevalence of growth retardation in the main group.

Importantly, tachypnea was recorded in 86.6% of children in the main group and in 61.6% of children in the comparison group. Physical lung examination findings in both groups depended on the volume and localization of pneumonic infiltration. On auscultation, 100% of children in the main group had diminished breath sounds and bronchophony, while 51.6% had localized crepitations at the site of the pathological process. In the comparison group, 45% of patients exhibited various wet and dry rales and prolonged expiration across the lung fields.

Regarding the cardiovascular system, muffled heart sounds were more frequently detected in 30.0% of children in the main group compared to 13.3% in the comparison group. A systolic murmur at the apex was noted in 25.0% of children in the main group versus 9.0% in the comparison group.

A key criterion for assessing the severity of the children's condition was the presence of respiratory failure (RF). RF grade I was diagnosed twice as often in the comparison group as in the main group (51.6% vs. 25.0%). RF grade II was observed at a similar frequency in both groups (35.0% and 33.3%, respectively). However, RF grade III was more commonly diagnosed in the main group (40.0%) compared to 15.0% in the comparison group, with these children requiring transfer to the intensive care unit.

Radiological examination (chest X-ray) results showed that bilateral focal-confluent pneumonia was diagnosed in 89% of children in the main group, compared to 34.5% in the comparison group. In other cases, unilateral focal pneumonia was observed.

Conclusions. Thus, in young children, pneumonia is characterized by an unfavorable premorbid background, artificial feeding, ENT pathology, and allergic diseases, which are complicated by bronchial obstruction syndrome. This necessitates differential diagnosis with acute obstructive bronchitis and the prescription of bronchodilator and anti-inflammatory therapy.

REFERENCES

1. Akhmedova, D.I., et al. (2006). Growth and development of children. pp. 37-49.
2. Bogdanova, A.V., Boitsova, E.V., Starevskaya, S.V., et al. (2022). Clinical features and course of bronchopulmonary dysplasia. *Pulmonology*, (1), 28-32.
3. Dementieva, G.M. (2024). Diseases of the bronchopulmonary system. 49 p.
4. Izaak, S.I., Panasyuk, T.V. (2015). *Pediatrics*, (3), 23-26.
5. Kuryazova, Sh., Khudaynazarova, S., & Dergunova, G. (2023). Community-acquired pneumonia in young school-age children with bronchial obstruction syndrome. *Journal of Biomedicine and Practice*, 1(2), 104–109. <https://doi.org/10.26739/2181-9300-2021-2-17>
6. Kuryazova, Sh., Khudaynazarova, S., & Toshmetova, B. (2023). Study of risk factors for the development of bronchopulmonary pathology in preschool children in the Aral Sea region.

Journal of Biomedicine and Practice, 1(1), 148–153. <https://doi.org/10.26739/2181-9300-2021-1-21>

7. Bolotskikh, V.I., Grebennikova, I.V., Makeeva, A.V., Kryukov, V.M., Tumanovsky, Yu.M., & Lidokhova, O.V. (2015). Features of pathological phenomena in childhood. *International Journal of Experimental Education*, (12-4), 564.
8. Practical guide on pediatric diseases: Respiratory diseases. Edited by B.M. Blokhin, V.F. Kokolina, A.G. Rumyantsev. Moscow: "MEDPRAKTIKA-M", 2007, pp. 14-16, 127-154, 222-232, 241-248.